

To the attention of the *DoRa Scholarship Committee*

here: Appendix for the Application for *DoRa Scholarship* for PhD Research Visit of Lemenkova Polina, M.Sc, PhD student of the *Technical University of Dresden*, for her research stay at the *University of Tartu, Faculty of Science and Technology, Institute of Ecology and Earth Sciences, Department of Geography, Chair of Geoinformatics and Cartography* Vanemuise 46, 51014 Tartu, Estonia

duration: two months, from the 01st of May 2012 until 30th of June 2012

Research Plan

for research stay of the visiting PhD student Lemenkova Polina at the *University of Tartu* during the period of May-June 2012, under the supervision of Assoc. Prof. Dr. Jüri Roosaare.

Research topic:

Spatial analysis of urban dynamics: effects of sociopolitical changes on landscape structure.

Region of Interest: Estonia, selected test sites (urban and sub-urban areas)

Research aim: 1) Multiscale mapping of land use patterns using remote sensing data
2) Spatial analysis of changes in landscape structure and urban sprawl.

Research purpose: application of advanced GIS technologies and remote sensing data to study changes in selected landscapes in Estonia, during the last 3 decades (1980-2010).

Technical background: The main software GIS tools are ArcGIS and Erdas Imagine.

Expected results:

- Analysis of the landscape dynamics caused by the economical and sociopolitical changes in country since 1990s: thematic maps of land use changes in selected sites, Estonia
- An article reporting the results of the research published in peer-reviewed journal (with focus on remote sensing / cartography)
- Report for the *DoRa Committee* resuming the results of the research

Detailed research plan (scheduled on two-week periods)

§ 1. 01 May – 15 May: **Defining test area, starting GIS project, data collecting & organizing.**

- 1) Data collecting. Main geo-data materials will be taken from the GIS open sources. These include aerial and satellite images covering different time span (10-20 years). Among available open sources we consider the following ones: Geoportal of the Estonian Land Board (<http://geoportaal.maaamet.ee>); satellite imagery from The Earth Explorer (<http://edcsns17.cr.usgs.gov/NewEarthExplorer/>), The Earth Science Data Interface (<http://glcfapp.glcf.umd.edu:8080/esdi/index.jsp>), GloVis (<http://glovis.usgs.gov/>),

aerial images (Google Earth), free Digital Elevation Models from the open source <http://geomorphometry.org/> , ASTER GDEM www.gdem.aster.ersdac.or.jp/ . Additionally, other available geodata may be used as well: descriptive data, shape files, materials from the department and university library (maps, books, reports and articles).

- 2) Data organizing. Preparing GIS project using *Arc Catalog / Arc Map* with remote sensing data and basic vector ground layers for GIS mapping (§ 3):
 - ✓ Ground layer showing relief, based on DEM, geological and topographic maps
 - ✓ Urban main infrastructure: street network, buildings, etc.
 - ✓ Land cover / use types and vegetation covering test sites
 - ✓ Satellite images of the research area taken in different time (last 20-30 years)

§ 2. 15 May – 01 June: **Image processing. Spatial analysis of land use patterns**

- 1) Environmental corridors: regional studies of natural land cover types, typical for the test areas. Changes in green patches and vegetation coverage. Application of the supervised classification (e.g., max. likelihood) to characterize main vegetation types and its dynamics (whether it is extending or regressing over time)
- 2) Spatial analysis of built-up areas in Estonia since sociopolitical changes in administrative structure of the country, to monitor landscape evolution:
 - a. sprawl of urban areas near major cities: dynamics over last 3 decades
 - b. suburban areas: intensification of housing and residential buildings
- 3) Overall landscape dynamics: overlay of the available data (aerial photographs, DEMs, vector layers and satellite images) using cartographic methods, to compare changes in landscape patterns at present and 20-30 years ago (time span 1980 - 2010).
The analysis of the landscape dynamics is based on the detected changes in imagery.

§ 3. 01 June – 15 June: **GIS Mapping**

Thematic mapping in Arc GIS, based on the results of the previous working step (§ 2, Image processing...): visualizing changes in landscape structures and land cover during the last decades (before and after great political changes) using overlay. Preparing final layouts.

§ 4. 15 June – 30 June: **Preparing final report and writing paper for publication**

1. The cartographic results should be visualized as 1-2 maps illustrating dynamics in land use in Estonia caused by global changes in political-administrative structure since 1990s.
2. Writing an article for the publication in a scientific journal (remote sensing):
“Effects of sociopolitical changes on urban sprawl: assessing landscape dynamics in Estonian suburban areas since 1980s”.
3. Preparing final report for the *DoRa Committee*.

Scientific chief:
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Jüri Roosaare

Visiting researcher:
Polina Lemenkova, M.Sc

27th of September, 2011.